

Research Article

The Investigation of Sink - Float Nature of Maiganga Coal

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Abstract

The Sink - Float analysis is a method of investigation of impurities bounded in coal using liquids of different specific gravities. A sample of 0.5kg of Maiganga coal was poured into a solution of zinc chloride having different densities of 1.00, 1.10, 1.20, 1.30, 1.40, 1.50, 1.60, 1.70, 1.80, 1.90 and 2.00. The floats and sinks in each of these densities were obtained and used to calculate the cumulative float, cumulative sink, instantaneous ash and distribution of ash; these values were then used to develop the respective partition curves (washability curve) which were obtained by plotting the partition coefficient against the mean of its density range. A sink - float problem was tested using the partition curves obtained. A yield of 80% was considered where the clean coal contains 16.45% ash with rejects of 70.18% ash separated at a specific gravity of 1.7. The separation with a distribution value of 5% becomes easy according to Burt (2004), Herbst (2005), Mills (2008) and Bird (2001) that if a low value less than 10% for the distribution is recorded, the separation becomes easy, while a value more than 20% gives a very difficult separation.

KEY WORDS: Sink - float Partition curve, dense media, Specific gravity, Ash

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Introduction

Coal may be broadly defined as a metamorphosed sedimentary rock of carbonaceous character in which the raw material has been supplied by plant of various group. The original plant material passes through many biomechanical and biochemical processes before it becomes a coal in technical terms (Lovell and Luckie, 2009). Coal is the

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combustible black or brownish black sedimentary rock which occurs in rock strata in layers or vein called coal beds or coal seams. The harder form such as anthracite can be regarded as metamorphic rock because of later exposure to elevated temperature and pressure (Mills et al., 2008)

Coal is a fossil fuel of altered remains of pre-historic vegetations that originally accumulated in swamps and peat bogs. Coal is composed primarily of carbon along with quantities of other elements chiefly hydrogen and oxygen with smaller quantity of sulphur, oxygen, nitrogen and silica (Jauro et al., 2003).

The energy we get from coal today comes from the energy that plant absorbed from the sun millions of years ago. All living plants store solar energy through a process known as photosynthesis: when plants die, the energy is usually released as the plants decay under favourable conditions of pressure and temperature. The decaying process is always interrupted, preventing the release of the stored solar energy that is locked into the coal. The quality of each coal deposit is determined by their:

- 1 Varying types of vegetation from which the coal originated.
- 2 Depths of burial.
- 3 Temperatures and pressures at those depths.
- 4 Length of time the coal has been formed in the deposits (Ojo and Akanide, 2004)

The degree of change coal undergoes as it matures from peat to lignite to sub-bituminous to bituminous and to anthracite is known as coalification. Coalification has an important bearing on coal's physical and chemical properties and it is referred to as the rank of the coal (Onuduko, 2014a). Ranking is determined by the degree of transformation of the original plants material to coal from those with the least carbon to those with the most carbon are lignite, sub bituminous, bituminous and anthracite (Chen, 2002; Anyanwu, 2009).

Carbonification is the process of coal metamorphism brought about by increasing weight of overriding sediments by tectonic movement with an increase in temperature resulting from depth of burial or from close approach to or contact with igneous intrusion or extrusion (Plitt and Kawatra, 2009). Coal as a fossil fuel is said to be a secondary process of all formation. Coal formation began during the carboniferous period known as the first coal age which spanned from 29 - 360 million years ago (U.S.A Energy Information Administration, 2008). During the tectonic movements - the build-up of silt and other sediments together with movements in the earth crust, plants, peat bogs and animal

remains were buried to great depths. The materials were subjected to high temperature and pressures, these caused physical and chemical changes in the vegetation, transforming it into peats and subsequently into coal (Outokmpu 2005; Sambo, 2009).

Analysis of coal can be proximate or ultimate. Proximate analysis is a technique that separates and identifies categories of compound in a mixture while ultimate analysis is used to determine the percentage of elements or constituents in the substance (Bird, 2001). The Float and Sink analysis of coal relates to a method and apparatus used to determine the theoretical yields of a coal at different impurities having passed through density of various floats. It is also a method and apparatus adoptable to determine the beneficiation prospect of coal ore. The beneficiation prospect of feed is evaluated by graphically developing a curve which indicates theoretically yield values of the concentrates quality in the plant (Godwin, 2013).

The float-sink analysis is a process of separation by density difference which is as old as a recorded history. Separation of minerals and gold in particular dates back to at least 3,000 years BC as indicated in writings from ancient Egypt (Herbst and Sepulveda, 2005). The separating action of a mineral by gravity separation depends on a particle's settling rate in a fluid. The evaluation of the separation method or performance of a gravity separation device is usually based on a sink-float analysis and washability curves. Many applications of the washability curves are applied to cleaning operations in the coal preparation so that most references are made to coal washability curves (Partition Enterprises, 2005). An ideal separation process would be one in which all particles of density lower than the separating density would be recovered in the light or clean coal product, and all materials denser than the separating density would be rejected as the heavy fraction, JKTech (2005) said this is not possible in practice. Material that is much heavier or lighter than the separating density tend to report to their proper fraction but as the density of the particle approaches the density of separation of the unit, the amount of misplaced material increases rapidly (Burt, 2005).

The characteristics needed for evaluating a unit performance are normally derived from a sink-float analysis of samples of the clean coal and the reject, followed by ash determinations of the various fractions. Usually, a sample of feed is also collected to determine its ash content to determine the yield (Gupta and Yan, 2006). A sink-float analysis is likened to a size analysis in that the sample is broken down into its various density fractions rather than size fractions. The sink-float test involves placing the sample progressively into baths of increasing density and recording the mass of sample within any given density fraction (AS 4156.1).

The aim of this research is to:

- (i) Examine the density of liquid at which the Maiganga coal can be separated into clean and reject.
- (ii) Determine the ash content of the fractions.
- (iii) Use the data obtained to produce partition curves to determine at any given density the percentage yield and the ease or difficulty of separation.

Research Methodology

The coal sample up to 2kg was obtained from different points within 2km² at the Maiganga Coal Mine, Akko Local Government Area of Gombe State, Nigeria. The sample was tied in a black bag to avoid oxidation. The coal samples were mixed together, air dried, crushed and sieved through a 25mm sieve.

The float - sink analysis was carried out in the chemistry laboratory of the department of Science Laboratory Technology, Plateau State Polytechnic Barkin Ladi. A 1kg weight of coal sample was ground to pass 1.18mm test sieve and the oversize coal was used for the various analysis. A 500g of the coal sample was measured and poured into zinc chloride which was diluted in 1000ml of water to obtain a solution of different specific gravities. The coal sample was poured into the first beaker containing the solution of zinc chloride of 1.0 specific gravity (SG) and stirred for 5 minutes and allowed to settle for three hours in order to obtain a float and a sink product. The float was scooped off and allowed to sun dry and was labelled as F1.00 while the solution was decanted from the sink using filter paper placed in a funnel in a conical flask. After decanting, the sink was labelled as S1.00, sun dried, weighed and put into the second beaker containing the solution of zinc chloride of 1.1 specific gravity, agitated and allowed to settle. The float was also obtained from this beaker, decanted, dried and weighed and labelled as F1.10, while the sink was rinsed, dried, weighed and labelled as S1.10 and then poured into the third beaker containing zinc chloride of higher density. This process was repeated using fluids of successive higher densities (1.2, 1.3, 1.4, 1.5, 1.6, 1.7, 1.8, 1.9 and 2.0) and labelled the floats as F1.20 up to F2.00 and S1.20 to S2.00 respectively until there was little or no float left. The solution of zinc chloride was decanted from the last sink of the coal, rewashed to remove any attached solution of zinc chloride, sundried, weighed, poured into a crucible and placed in a muffle furnace and fired four five hours at a temperature of 850°C until ash was obtained.

Results

The fractions at different densities starting from F1.00 and S1.00 represented the material that floated at a specific gravity of 1.00 and those that sank at a specific gravity of 1.00. The densities of the zinc chloride were subsequently increased up to 2.00. The mass of samples that lies within the corresponding density range was the grade of the particles in the

density fractions at ash percentage. The amount of ash (mass) in the density of the fraction obtained lists the nominal density of the fraction taken at the floating density. The cumulative value of both float and sink and the associated ash contents were summed from the top down and from the bottom of the table up for the sink respectively. The cumulative grade (weighted average) of the combined floats up to the nominal density of sink was also equal the sample grade when the instantaneous ash which represents the highest ash content of any individual ash particle on the float at that density was calculated. The distribution of the ash was also calculated in each of the fractions.

Figure 1.0: Cumulative Floats

Figure 1.0 shows the cumulative floats graph obtained by plotting the cumulative mass percent of floats at each relative density increment against the cumulative ash at that point. The graph is used to give the yield obtainable for any ash required.

Figure 2.0: Cumulative Sinks

This graph was arrived at by plotting the cumulative mass percent sinks at each relative density increment against the cumulative ash of the sinks for that separation. The graph is used to calculate the ash content of the rejects when a particular yield of clean coal is needed (FonteinDijksman, 2002).

Figure 3.0: Instantaneous Ash

Taggart (2005) says, the instantaneous ash partition curve is a derivation of the cumulative percent ash in the floats and indicates the rate of change of the ash content at different specific gravities of yields. It is the highest ash content of any individual particle in the floats at any density.

Figure 4.0: Relative Density

Relative density is obtained by plotting the cumulative percent of floats against the relative density for that separation (Heavy Liquids, 2005). It determines the yield of clean coal for a perfect separation at a selected relative density.

Table 5.0: Distribution

A density interval in most cases ± 0.01 (0.05) for specific gravity is specified and then the difference in yield, that is the cumulative floats between two relative densities, 0.2 apart, is plotted against the mean of those densities (Burt, 2004; Herbst, 2005; Mills, 2008 and Bird, 2001). The graph above represents the percentage of the feed that was close to any particular separating density or the percentage of near gravity of a material in the feed. This graph depicts the ease or difficulty in the separation of coal.

Sink – Float Test Data

If a yield at a certain percentage is to be determined, the washability curves or graphs in Figures 1.0, 2.0, 4.0 and 5.0 are used. Like, if the yield of 80% is to be determined then the clean coal will be 16.45% ash (Figure 1.0) and the rejects will contain 70.18% ash (Figure 2.0). The separation will be done at 1.7 specific gravity (Figure 4.0), with ease (distribution graph reading = 5) (Figure 5.0). According to Burt (2004), Herbst (2005), Mills (2008) and Bird (2001) that if a low value less than 10% is read from the distribution graph, the separation becomes satisfactory and easy to separate, while a value more than 20% gives a very difficult separation.

Conclusion

The washability or partition curves from the sink - float analysis of Maiganga coal practically indicates that the yield of clean coal at 80% contained 16.45% ash and rejects of 70.18% ash. This separation was done at a specific gravity of 1.7 and the value of distribution being 5.0% indicating the ease at which it can be separated. Again, if the clean coal at 50% is needed it will contain 11.1% ash and 43.9% rejects separating at a specific gravity of 1.3 with the value of distribution of 50.5%. This will become very difficult to separate. In the overall, the coal seems to be separated with difficulty at low specific gravity and easy to separate with low ash content at high specific gravity. The clean coal with

minimal ash can be used in the generation of electric or thermal power and as fossil fuel in rail locomotive steam boat.

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